

A DIGIT REVERSAL PROPERTY FOR STERN POLYNOMIALS

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Abstract

We consider the following polynomial generalization of Stern's diatomic series: let $s_1(x, y) = 1$, and for $n \geq 1$ set $s_{2n}(x, y) = s_n(x, y)$ and $s_{2n+1}(x, y) = x s_n(x, y) + y s_{n+1}(x, y)$. The coefficient $[x^i y^j] s_n(x, y)$ is the number of hyperbinary expansions of $n - 1$ with exactly i occurrences of the digit 2 and j occurrences of 0. We prove that the polynomials s_n are invariant under *digit reversal*, that is, $s_n = s_{n^R}$, where n^R is obtained from n by reversing the binary expansion of n .

1. Introduction

The Stern sequence (also called Stern's diatomic sequence or Stern–Brocot sequence) s is defined by the recurrence $s_1 = 1$, $s_{2n} = s_n$ and $s_{2n+1} = s_n + s_{n+1}$. It was pointed out by Dijkstra [4], [3, pp.230–232] that this sequence satisfies a symmetry property with respect to reversal of the binary expansion of n . More precisely, for a positive integer n having the proper base-2 expansion $n = (\varepsilon_\nu \varepsilon_{\nu-1} \dots \varepsilon_0)_2$ we define

$$n^R = \sum_{0 \leq i \leq \nu} \varepsilon_{\nu-i} 2^i = (\varepsilon_0 \varepsilon_1 \dots \varepsilon_\nu)_2.$$

Theorem A (Dijkstra). $s_n = s_{n^R}$.

Stern's diatomic sequence is closely related to continued fractions (see Stern [14], Lehmer [10], Lind [11], Graham, Knuth, Patashnik [8, Exercise 6.50]): if $n = (1^{k_0} 0^{k_1} \dots 1^{k_{r-2}} 0^{k_{r-1}} 1^{k_r})_2$, then s_n is the numerator of the continued fraction $[k_0; k_1, \dots, k_r]$. Theorem A is therefore the same as the statement that $[k_0; k_1, \dots, k_r]$ and $[k_r; k_{r-1}, \dots, k_0]$ have the same numerator, which can be proved via continuants.

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In [12], Morgenbesser and the author proved a digit reversal property for the correlation

$$\gamma_t(\alpha) = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{0 \leq n < N} e(\alpha \sigma_q(n+t) - \alpha \sigma_q(n)),$$

where $e(x) = \exp(2\pi i x)$ and $\sigma_q(n)$ is the sum of digits of n in base q ($q \geq 2$ an integer). That is, we proved that $\gamma_t(\alpha) = \gamma_{tR}(\alpha)$, where the digit reversal is in base q . We note that for the case $q = 2$ this statement is a special case of Theorem 1 below.

In this paper, we wish to give a refinement of Theorem A, concerning *hyperbinary expansions*. A hyperbinary expansion [5] of a nonnegative integer n is a sequence $(\varepsilon_{\nu-1}, \dots, \varepsilon_0) \in \{0, 1, 2\}^\nu$ such that $\sum_{0 \leq i < \nu} \varepsilon_i 2^i = n$. We call such an expansion *proper* if either $\nu = 0$ or $\nu > 0$ and $\varepsilon_{\nu-1} \neq 0$. Since we only work with proper expansions, we will usually omit the prefix “proper”. By induction, using the defining recurrence relation, it is not difficult to see that s_n is the number of hyperbinary expansions of $n - 1$ (see also Proposition 1, which generalizes this property). This property is stated as Theorem 5.2 in [13], which seems to be the earliest (correct) appearance in the literature — we note that the statement on the bottom of page 275 of [2] is erroneous, which can be seen considering the case $n = 5$. The same statement can be found on page 57 of [11].

2. Main Results

Our main theorem generalizes Theorem A. We define bivariate polynomials $s_n(x, y)$ by

$$\begin{aligned} s_1(x, y) &= 1, \\ s_{2n}(x, y) &= s_n(x, y), \\ s_{2n+1}(x, y) &= x s_n(x, y) + y s_{n+1}(x, y). \end{aligned}$$

Note that this definition of Stern polynomials differs from the one given in [6] and also from the definition in [9]. However, the univariate polynomials $s_n(x, 1)$ appear, up to a shift of the index n , in the article [1] by Bates and Mansour: the authors write “[...]the n th term $f(n; q)$ of the q -analogue of the Calkin–Wilf sequence is the generating function for the number of hyperbinary expansions of n according to the number of powers that are used exactly twice.” This should be compared with Proposition 1 below. Moreover, $s_n(x, 1)$ appears as the special case $t = 1$ in [5] (see (1.2), (1.3) in that paper). The bivariate polynomial $s_n(x, y)$, however, appears to be a new object of study. We list the first few of these polynomials: we have

$$s_1(x, y) = 1, \qquad s_2(x, y) = 1,$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 s_3(x, y) &= x + y, & s_4(x, y) &= 1, \\
 s_5(x, y) &= x + xy + y^2, & s_6(x, y) &= x + y, \\
 s_7(x, y) &= x^2 + xy + y, & s_8(x, y) &= 1, \\
 s_9(x, y) &= x + xy + xy^2 + y^3, & s_{10}(x, y) &= x + xy + y^2, \\
 s_{11}(x, y) &= x^2 + xy + y^2 + x^2y + xy^2, & s_{12}(x, y) &= x + y, \\
 s_{13}(x, y) &= x^2 + xy + y^2 + x^2y + xy^2, & s_{14}(x, y) &= x^2 + xy + y, \\
 s_{15}(x, y) &= y + xy + x^3 + x^2y, & s_{16}(x, y) &= 1, \\
 s_{17}(x, y) &= x + xy + xy^2 + xy^3 + y^4, & s_{18}(x, y) &= x + xy + xy^2 + y^3, \\
 s_{19}(x, y) &= x^2 + xy + x^2y + xy^2 + y^3 + x^2y^2 + xy^3, & s_{20}(x, y) &= x + xy + y^2, \\
 s_{21}(x, y) &= x^2 + 2x^2y + 2xy^2 + y^3 + x^2y^2 + xy^3, & s_{22}(x, y) &= x^2 + xy + y^2 \\
 & & & + x^2y + xy^2, \\
 s_{23}(x, y) &= xy + y^2 + x^3 + x^2y + xy^2 + x^3y + x^2y^2, & s_{24}(x, y) &= x + y, \\
 s_{25}(x, y) &= x^2 + xy + x^2y + xy^2 + y^3 + x^2y^2 + xy^3, & s_{26}(x, y) &= x^2 + xy + y^2 \\
 & & & + x^2y + xy^2
 \end{aligned}$$

and we see the notable identities $s_{11}(x, y) = s_{13}(x, y)$ and $s_{19}(x, y) = s_{25}(x, y)$, where $13 = 11^R$ and $25 = 19^R$. In fact, we have the following symmetry property generalizing Theorem A.

Theorem 1. *Let n be a positive integer. Then*

$$s_n(x, y) = s_{n^R}(x, y).$$

This theorem can be translated to a statement on hyperbinary expansions. For integers $i, j \geq 0$ and $t \geq 1$ let $h_{i,j}(t)$ be the number of proper hyperbinary expansions $(\varepsilon_{\nu-1}, \dots, \varepsilon_0)$ of $t - 1$ such that $|\{\ell : 0 \leq \ell < \nu, \varepsilon_\ell = 2\}| = i$ and $|\{\ell : 0 \leq \ell < \nu, \varepsilon_\ell = 0\}| = j$. The following proposition connects the Stern polynomials $s_n(x, y)$ to hyperbinary expansions.

Proposition 1. *Assume that $n \geq 1$ is an integer. Then*

$$\sum_{i,j \geq 0} h_n(i, j)x^i y^j = s_n(x, y).$$

In other words, we have $h_n(i, j) = [x^i y^j] s_n(x, y)$, that is, the polynomial $s_n(x, y)$ encodes the number of hyperbinary expansions of $n - 1$ having a given number of 2s and 0s. Let us illustrate this proposition by an example. The polynomial $s_{21}(x, y)$ can be obtained by listing the hyperbinary expansions of 20:

1212	x^2	1220	x^2y
2012	x^2y	2100	xy^2

$$\begin{array}{cc} 10012 & xy^2 \\ 2020 & x^2y^2 \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{cc} 10100 & y^3 \\ 10020 & xy^3. \end{array}$$

Combining Theorem 1 and Proposition 1, we immediately get the following corollary.

Corollary 1. *Let $n \geq 1$ and $i, j \geq 0$. We have*

$$h_n(i, j) = h_{n^R}(i, j).$$

For example, we list the hyperbinary expansions of $18 = (10011)_2 - 1$ (first row) and $24 = (11001)_2 - 1$ (second row):

$$\begin{array}{cccccc} 10010 & 2010 & 1210 & 10002 & 2002 & 1202 & 1122 \\ 11000 & 10120 & 10112 & 10200 & 2200 & 2120 & 2112 \end{array}$$

By the corollary there is a one-to-one correspondence between these expansions.

3. Proofs

3.1. Proof of Theorem 1

The main argument, which represents the induction step in the proof of the theorem, is the following lemma.

Lemma 1. *Let*

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ x & y \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad B = \begin{pmatrix} x & y \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

If tA denotes the transpose of the matrix A , the following identities for 1×2 -matrices hold.

$$\begin{aligned} (x \ y) AA &= (-y) (x \ y) + (y + 1) (x \ y) A, \\ (1 \ 1) {}^tA {}^tA &= (-y) (1 \ 1) + (y + 1) (1 \ 1) {}^tA, \\ (x \ y) AB &= x (x \ y) + y (x \ y) B, \\ (1 \ 1) {}^tA {}^tB &= x (1 \ 1) + y (1 \ 1) {}^tB, \\ (x \ y) BA &= y (x \ y) + x (x \ y) A, \\ (1 \ 1) {}^tB {}^tA &= y (1 \ 1) + x (1 \ 1) {}^tA, \\ (x \ y) BB &= (-x) (x \ y) + (x + 1) (x \ y) B, \\ (1 \ 1) {}^tB {}^tB &= (-x) (1 \ 1) + (x + 1) (1 \ 1) {}^tB. \end{aligned}$$

The proof is by simple calculation and is left to the reader. □

To prove Theorem 1, we let $n \geq 1$ be an odd integer. This is no loss of generality since we can deal with the even case by repeatedly using the relation $s_{2n}(x, y) = s_n(x, y)$. Let $n = \sum_{i \leq \nu} \varepsilon_i 2^i$ be the binary representation of n and $\varepsilon_\nu \neq 0$. We prove the theorem by induction on ν . The case $\nu \leq 1$ is trivial, since in this case we have $n^R = n$. We write $A(0) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ x & y \end{pmatrix}$ and $A(1) = \begin{pmatrix} x & y \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$. By a simple application of the recurrence relation we have $\binom{s_{2n}}{s_{2n+1}} = A(0) \binom{s_n}{s_{n+1}}$ and $\binom{s_{2n+1}}{s_{2n+2}} = A(1) \binom{s_n}{s_{n+1}}$ for all $n \geq 1$. Since n is odd and $s_1(x, y) = s_2(x, y) = 1$, it follows from these identities that

$$s_n(x, y) = \begin{pmatrix} x & y \end{pmatrix} A(\varepsilon_1) \cdots A(\varepsilon_{\nu-1}) \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}. \tag{1}$$

The statement of the theorem is equivalent to the assertion that

$$\begin{pmatrix} x & y \end{pmatrix} A(\varepsilon_1) \cdots A(\varepsilon_{\nu-1}) \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} {}^t A(\varepsilon_1) \cdots {}^t A(\varepsilon_{\nu-1}) \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \end{pmatrix} \tag{2}$$

for all $\nu \geq 1$ and all finite sequences $(\varepsilon_1, \dots, \varepsilon_{\nu-1})$ in $\{0, 1\}$. We prove the identity (2) by induction on ν , using Lemma 1. This identity is obvious for $\nu \leq 2$. For $\nu > 2$ we have four cases, corresponding to the four possible values of $(\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2)$. By Lemma 1, in each of the four cases there exist coefficients α and β such that

$$\begin{pmatrix} x & y \end{pmatrix} A(\varepsilon_1)A(\varepsilon_2) = \alpha \begin{pmatrix} x & y \end{pmatrix} + \beta \begin{pmatrix} x & y \end{pmatrix} A(\varepsilon_2)$$

and

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} {}^t A(\varepsilon_1){}^t A(\varepsilon_2) = \alpha \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} + \beta \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} {}^t A(\varepsilon_2).$$

By applying the induction hypothesis (2) to the sequences $(\varepsilon_2, \dots, \varepsilon_{\nu-1})$ and $(\varepsilon_3, \dots, \varepsilon_{\nu-1})$ we obtain the statement of the theorem. □

3.2. Proof of Proposition 1

In order to prove Proposition 1, we use the following recurrence for $h_n(i, j)$ (see [7]).

Proposition 2. *Let $n \geq 1$. Then*

$$\begin{aligned} h_1(0, 0) &= 1, \\ h_1(i, j) &= 0 && \text{for } (i, j) \neq (0, 0), \\ h_{2n}(i, j) &= h_n(i, j) && \text{for } i, j \geq 0, \\ h_{2n+1}(i, 0) &= h_n(i - 1, 0) && \text{for } i \geq 1, \\ h_{2n+1}(0, j) &= h_{n+1}(0, j - 1) && \text{for } j \geq 1, \\ h_{2n+1}(i, j) &= h_n(i - 1, j) + h_{n+1}(i, j - 1) && \text{for } i, j \geq 1. \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

Moreover, $h_t(0, 0) = 0$ if t is not a power of 2.

Proof. The first two lines follow from the fact that the empty tuple $()$ is the only hyperbinary expansion of 0.

The hyperbinary expansions of $2n - 1$ are in bijection with the hyperbinary expansions of $n - 1$ by deleting the lowest digit, which is a 1. This explains the third line of (3).

A hyperbinary expansion of $2n$ without 0 necessarily ends with the digit 2, and the bijection is by deleting this digit. This gives line number four.

There is exactly one hyperbinary expansion of $2n$ without 2, and it ends with 0. The same argument applies here.

The sixth line is a combination of arguments as above.

Finally, integers having the binary expansion $(1 \cdots 1)$ are the only ones without 0 and 2, which proves the last line. \square

In order to prove Proposition 1, we proceed by induction. The identity is trivial for $n = 1$. Assume that $n = 2u$ for some $u \geq 1$. We have $h_n(i, j) = h_u(i, j)$ and $s_n(x, y) = s_u(x, y)$. If $n = 2u + 1$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\substack{i \geq 0 \\ j \geq 0}} h_n(i, j)x^i y^j &= h_n(0, 0) + \sum_{j \geq 1} h_n(0, j)y^j + \sum_{i \geq 1} h_n(i, 0)x^i + \sum_{i, j \geq 1} h_n(i, j)x^i y^j \\ &= \sum_{j \geq 1} h_{u+1}(0, j - 1)y^j + \sum_{i \geq 1} h_u(i - 1, 0)x^i \\ &+ \sum_{i, j \geq 1} (h_u(i - 1, j) + h_{u+1}(i, j - 1))x^i y^j \\ &+ \sum_{\substack{i \geq 1 \\ j \geq 0}} h_u(i - 1, j)x^i y^j + \sum_{\substack{i \geq 0 \\ j \geq 1}} h_u(i, j - 1)x^i y^j \\ &= x s_u(x, y) + y s_{u+1}(x, y) = s_n(x, y), \end{aligned}$$

which proves the desired assertion. \square

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